

RADx-UP

Community Collaboration Grant Program

SUCCESSES AND INSIGHTS FROM 2020 TO 2024

RADx-UP

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Successes and Insights from 2020-2024

Introduction

The Community Collaboration Grant (C2G) program was created under the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics in Underserved Populations Coordination and Data Collection Center (RADx-UP CDCC). Charged with expanding the geographic and population-specific reach of the RADx-UP program (Figure 1), the C2G program supported community partners in advancing capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives among communities adversely affected by COVID-19.

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RADx-UP | Total Number of C2G | RADx-UP Funded Projects by State (C2G N = 70* | RADx-UP N = 137**)

Engagement in the evaluation and adoption of established and new diagnostic tests by communities adversely affected by COVID-19 was critical to reducing the disease burden in the United States. This program provided CDCC subawards to increase the capacity for COVID-19 testing expertise within the community. These CDCC grant funds could be used to support personnel costs, contracted service costs (e.g., participant transportation, translation, and interpretation, etc.), and non-personnel costs (e.g., other participant incentives, information and technology equipment) necessary to:

- Remove barriers to COVID-19 communication and outreach, COVID-19 testing and diagnosis, and COVID-19 data collection and dissemination testing
- Develop communities of practice between community collaboration CDCC mini-grant sub-awardees and current RADx-UP awardees which would extend communication and outreach, expand testing availability, and enhance data collection and dissemination capacities
- Evaluate strategies for the communication of test results and follow-up measures to underserved and vulnerable populations
- Provide training and education for community members around COVID-19 testing topics of interest to the community
- Provide funding for community personnel training on specific aspects of COVID-19 related research including informatics, data collection methods, standardized survey administration, and others
- Provide funding to increase capacity for COVID-19 testing activities in the community
- Generate communication materials related to COVID-19 testing
- Collaborate with CEAL programs on activities such as understanding attitudes about testing and vaccines

The C2G program was open to community-serving organizations (CBOs), faith-based organizations (FBOs), community-based clinics, and tribal nations and organizations. The RADx-UP CDCC began soliciting C2G applications on February 26, 2021 and closed its last application cycle on April 23, 2023. The program received a total of 209 applications across seven cycles and funded a total of 70 projects (33%). Investing over \$3.7 million dollars in supporting organizations in 27 states (**Figure 2**), the C2G program helped organizations increase training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, and contact tracing in communities.

The funded projects helped to decrease COVID-19 transmission and save lives.

Figure 3. Underserved and COVID-19 vulnerable populated served by C2G projects

Evaluation Strategy

In collaboration with the Abacus Evaluation team at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, the C2G awardees were engaged at three-time points (6 months, 12 months, and 18 months) to gather data on their project updates, activities, outcomes, and use of CDCC support and resources. In addition to evaluating the impact of the awardees' projects, we evaluated the impact and effectiveness of the C2G program overall.

The 6-month interim and 12-month closeout progress report surveys were emailed to awardees based on their project start dates. The brief online surveys assessed progress on project activities, information on collaborations, populations engaged, project roadblocks, and the use of CDCC resources.

At 18 months from the project start date (six months post-project), awardees were engaged in 20-minute Zoom interviews with the UNC evaluation team to assess longer-term impacts of the pilot projects, including any sustained project activities and other achievements that stemmed from the pilot project (e.g., additional external funding or new partnerships).

Project Impact

C2G projects conducted outreach in their communities to bring awareness to facts about COVID-19, reducing transmission, and building trust within their communities. The main approaches used by the awardees to achieve the aims of the C2G program were to establish ongoing community presence and host events as trusted sites and trusted community voices.

These included:

- Assisting individuals in accessing testing appointments and distributing free test kits
- Sending out self-testing kits with video instructions and resources on prevention and treatment
- Educating those with limited health literacy
- Disseminating bilingual COVID-19 testing information and policy updates through webinars, bilingual social media platforms, and call centers to expand community outreach
- Facilitating collaborative focus group discussions and the flow of trusted government resources to the limited English-speaking community
- Launching impactful social media campaigns, vaccination clinics, and testing services
- Developing educational videos, brochures, and newsletters to reduce information gaps
- Providing services to hard-to-reach populations including homeless individuals and those with mental illness

In addition to serving as trusted community voices, many of the organizations partnered with other trusted organizations throughout their communities. These organization types varied from community centers, faith-based organizations, medical centers, to schools and daycares. (Figure 4)

Partner Organization Types by Cycle

Notes: One project can have more than one partner organization

Figure 4. Characteristics of C2G Project Partners (n= 49 projects reporting)

C2G projects have had an immense impact on COVID-19 awareness in their communities. As of February 29, 2024, fifty-five project teams across six funding cycles reached over 786,900 people across all project activities. (Figure 5) These data are based on the reach described in the 12-month survey responses. The project activities that contributed to the overall reach included social media campaigns, digital ads, community pop-up events, door-to-door canvassing, and dissemination of educational materials. Notably, Cycle 7 projects have made the largest impact, reaching 9,942,219 people within the first 6 months of their funding cycle. A large portion of this number, 9,913,600, is attributed to a social media and digital ad campaign started by the Rhode Island Public Health Institute.

Figure 5. The Reach of C2G Project Partners

Other key impact activities by the funded projects:

- Provided COVID-19 testing to communities at no cost
- Increased capacity for COVID-19 testing through education and training of non-clinical staff
- Promoted healthcare accessibility and equity for all to receive testing and vaccination services through culturally sensitive and bilingual training of volunteers
- Promotion of COVID-19 education and testing among underserved community populations through the hosting of community events
- Increased community knowledge of precautions to be taken to avoid COVID-19 infection
- Increased capacity for COVID-19 testing and vaccination through education and outreach

- Increased uptake in school testing
- Developed a phone line service to provide an avenue for communication of test results and follow-up
- Utilized a mobile testing unit to provide COVID-19 testing and vaccination services to communities
- Mitigated medical and government mistrust in vulnerable populations to improve health care access and quality

Although the C2G project teams were able to have a substantial impact on their communities, they had to overcome many challenges faced by members of their communities. These challenges included, but were not limited to:

- Social barriers in the form of misinformation, cultural barriers, language barriers, and general socioeconomic risk factors such as access to basic health resources
- Lack of access to transportation to take individuals to and from appointments for treatment or testing
- Hesitation to receive treatment or testing due to the fear of being deported or separated from families
- Standard hours of operation at testing and/or treatment facilities that limited individuals' ability to receive testing and vaccinations, especially those jobs that do not offer paid sick leave
- COVID-19 fatigue

The funded projects also had to overcome internal challenges such as their ability to disseminate information in rural/remote areas, decrease in resources and staffing, and delays in receiving testing kits. While some project teams were able to overcome these challenges, others had to pivot and restructure their projects. Nonetheless, all organizations were able to successfully complete their projects' objectives while gathering insights for future work.

The projects undertaken by C2G awardees provided insight into the demand, necessity, and value of community-based and community-driven research. To help inform future funding opportunities and community-centered work, lessons learned were documented. Projects highlighted the importance of consistently building trust with underserved communities, open communication, and meeting community members where they were located. Strategies to build trust focused on partnering with the community in the design of the program, utilizing non-clinical community members to reach their neighbors, and developing projects with a culturally and linguistically responsive approach. Open communication strategies focused

on creating and distributing COVID-19 information through pamphlets and flyers in multiple languages, utilizing social media to disseminate information, and engaging community members with strong rapport and understanding of the community population to speak at events. Strategies for meeting community members where they were located included the use of mobile clinics. These mobile clinics expanded testing and vaccine availability by eliminating the difficulty of taking time off work to travel. Above all, the C2G awardees emphasized the importance of having the ability and willingness to pivot and be flexible in public health emergencies.

Conclusion

The RADx-UP Community Collaboration Grant program has been highly successful. With an emphasis on serving underserved and Covid-19 vulnerable communities in the United States, the program supported 70 projects across 27 states. As of February 29, 2024, the first 55 projects had already reached 786,900 people through efforts that included Covid-19 outreach and education, vaccination, and testing. In doing so, they overcame common barriers to access to health services including misinformation, language, transportation, and trust. To overcome these barriers, successful C2G awardees formed partnerships with community members to design their program, provided culturally- and linguistically-responsive services, created social media campaigns and mobile clinics to serve community members both online and in person. Future NIH initiatives to improve health and health services in underserved and vulnerable communities in the U.S. can benefit from the RADx-UP approach by establishing similar community collaboration grant programs.

APPENDIX: Examples of Organizational Profiles

The Drs. Aaron and Olye Shirley Foundation is a nonprofit organization established to honor the lives of Dr. Aaron Shirley and Dr. Olye Shirley, who spent their lives and professional careers concerned with the health and well-being of people in underserved communities. The Foundation utilizes a collaborative community-based approach to coordinate and/or offer programs to educate, enlighten, monitor, equip, and offer resources to help improve community members' physical and mental conditions.

C2G PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The **Removing Barriers to COVID-19 Testing in Mississippi** resulted in:

- **177 COVID-19 tests** administered through testing events in communities that were at least 20 miles from a health center.
- **56 vaccines and 120 booster shots** administered
- **Partnerships** with Mallory Community Health Center, The Institute for the Advancement of Minority Health, Holmes County Health Network, and several faith-based organizations.
- **20 community members** winning a \$25 Walmart gift card.

C2G PROJECT SUMMARY

This project aimed to increase access to COVID-19 testing for minorities in rural and underserved communities. The Shirley Foundation utilized a community-based COVID-19 coordinated response team to develop a culturally appropriate mitigation strategy by:

- **Developing culturally appropriate messaging** to educate the community on the importance of COVID-19 testing.
- **Implementing a community outreach strategy** with faith-based and community-based organizations by conducting webinars and utilizing social media to inform how to access COVID-19 testing.
- **Utilizing a community health worker** to schedule testing for those unable to navigate the online system
- **Collaborating with Mallory Community Health Center and On-Site Health** for mobile testing for community members without transportation.

The Community You Serve

Drs. Aaron and Olye Shirley Foundation serves underserved urban and rural communities that are considered Health Professional Shortage Areas.

The community is predominantly African American, and 30% live in poverty. Additionally, the community suffers from at least one chronic health condition: obesity, diabetes, and heart disease.

The Engagement

The Drs. Aaron and Olyye Shirley Foundation:

- Community engagement afforded us relationships with other community-based and faith-based organizations.
- Our collaboration with FQHCs allowed us to develop a relationship with the Mayor of Pickens, who became a new partner in health fairs.
- Our community health worker was frequently featured on local radio stations to discuss and promote events and the project.
- Some of the project activities were featured on the local news stations.

The Future

In the next 5 years, we hope to have established the Drs. Aaron and Olyye Shirley Foundation is a research community-based organization that utilizes data to influence policy that supports health and education equity.

Our goal is to develop a data hub to use to implement interventions for the underserved population in Mississippi.

The team:

Terrence Shirley - President
Erin Shirley Orey – Program Manager
Christal S. Porter – Grants Admin
Joyce Roundtree-McCoy - CHW

Find out more:

<https://theshirleyfoundation.org/>

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Removing Barriers to COVID-19 Testing in Mississippi

During the coronavirus pandemic, studies have shown that although African Americans are 13.4% of the population in the U.S., data shows for African Americans and other minorities, the infection and death rates are significantly higher than Whites. African Americans are dying at a rate 2.5 times higher than Whites. Access to COVID-19 testing will help mitigate COVID-19.

RADx-UP CDCC
Community Collaboration
Grant Program

IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The project resulted in clinical and community/public health benefits.

This project was able to provide COVID-19 testing and other health screenings to minorities in underserved communities that were at least 20 miles away from a community health center or physician's office by bringing testing resources to them.

The Challenge

The Mississippi Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (MS BRFSS) reported in 2018 that approximately 60% of Mississippians suffered from at least one chronic health condition.² Additionally, the MS BRFSS data show that the following chronic health conditions: obesity, diabetes, heart disease and lung disease, are more prevalent in African Americans and low-income households, which all are risk factors for COVID-19.² In Mississippi, there have been 309,000 COVID-19 cases and 7,139 deaths during the pandemic.

The Approach

The main goal for this project is to develop a culturally appropriate mitigation strategy for providing equitable access to COVID-19 testing.

- Activity 1: Develop culturally appropriate messaging to educate the community of the importance of COVID-19 testing.
- Activity 2: Implement a community outreach strategy with faith-based and community-based organizations by conducting webinars and utilizing social media to inform how to access COVID-19 testing.
- Activity 3: Collaborate with Mallory Community Health Center and On-Site Health for mobile COVID-19 testing.

Translational
Science
Benefits Model¹

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

Removing Barriers to COVID-19 Testing in Mississippi

Served Black/African American, socioeconomically disadvantaged, underserved rural, and sexual and gender minority populations

Resulted in:

177 COVID-19 tests administered through testing events

56 vaccines and 120 booster shots administered

Key Benefits

CLINICAL

Performed tests in underserved, minority populations to diagnose COVID-19.

COMMUNITY

Allowed mitigation of issues related to location to drive forth equity in accessing COVID-19 related preventative resources from the health care system.

COMMUNITY

Organized awareness of public health services benefits through culturally appropriate outreach strategies.

The Team: The Drs. Aaron and Olye Shirley Foundation; The Institute for the Advancement of Minority Health; Six Dimensions, LLC; Magnolia Medical Foundation

Contact: Erin Shirley Orey- Program Manager, Drs. Aaron and Olye Shirley Foundation; Email: ErinRShirley@gmail.com

Find out more: <http://theshirleyfoundation.org/>

¹ Institute of Clinical & Translational Sciences at Washington University in St. Louis. Translational Science Benefits Model website. <https://translationalsciencebenefits.wustl.edu>. Published February 1, 2019. Accessed May 31, 2022.

² Zhang, L., McLeod, S. T., Vargas, R., Liu, X., Young, D. K., & Dobbs, T. E. (2020). Subgroup comparison of COVID-19 case and mortality with associated factors in Mississippi: findings from analysis of the first four months of public data. *The Journal of Biomedical Research*, 34(6), 446. <https://doi.org/10.7555/jbr.34.20200135>

Founded in 1973, Korean Community Services of Metropolitan New York, Inc (KCS) is the oldest and largest 501(c)(3) nonprofit organization assisting Korean immigrants and other underserved communities residing in the New York City area. The mission at KCS is to serve as a bridge for immigrants, helping them to address their critical needs, and assisting them in overcoming any social, economic, or health-related barriers.

C2G PROJECT SUMMARY

Many faith-based organizations (FBOs) occupy a uniquely elevated and prominent position within their local communities. Moreover, faith leaders possess considerable influence, trust, language and cultural competencies, and intimate connections with congregants and community members. KCS **leveraged its longstanding experience** partnering with local FBOs and leading multi-organizational coalitions **to provide dedicated testing services and culturally tailored COVID-19 outreach and education for underserved community members** as part of “Get Tested Queens.” Furthermore, based on the demonstrated efficacy of delivering public health initiatives in partnership with FBOs, KCS **partnered with four FBOs** strategically located within each of the target neighborhoods.

The Community You Serve

KCS envisions a world where immigrant communities remain grounded in their heritage and work together with the broader community to build a better society at large. KCS’ mission is to be a bridge for Korean immigrants and the wider Asian community to fully integrate into society and overcome any economic, health and linguistic barriers so that they become independent and thriving members of the community. They accomplish this mission by providing culturally competent programs in the areas of Aging, Education, Immigration, Workforce Development, Public Health and Mental Health.

C2G PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The Get Tested Queens project resulted in:

- Creating **healthier and safer communities** by **providing easy access to COVID-19 testing and education**
- Fostering **strong bonds** between community members and their faith-based organizations
- **5424 people reached** as part of testing efforts
- **270 testing and outreach events held**

The Engagement

With seven locations across the metro area, KCS offers a range of professional and culturally competent service programs through their:

- [Public Health & Research Center](#)
- [Workforce Development program](#)
- [Senior centers](#)
- Adult Daycare Center
- and [Mental Health Clinic](#).

Most pertinently, KCS' [health services serve local immigrants](#) and other underserved communities by facilitating access to healthcare, providing free screenings, education, and patient navigation services. These services are also provided through a robust network of community stakeholders which we have cultivated through many years of service including local CBOs, FBOs, clinical partners, academic institutions, government agencies, and media groups.

To learn more about the services offered at Korean Community Services of Metropolitan New York visit: <https://www.kcsny.org/>

The Get Tested Queens Project

Recognizing the unique role that faith-based organizations play in the lives of individuals from minority and communities of color, Korean Community Services of Metropolitan New York's Get Tested Queens COVID-19 testing project directly partners with these trusted institutions and their leaders to provide COVID-19 testing and culturally tailored outreach for underserved community members who have been hardest hit by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Translational Science
Benefits Model

IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The project helped **make healthier and safer communities** by **providing easy access to COVID-19 testing and education**. It promoted **strong bonds** between community members and their faith-based organizations. The organizations **gained more trust** from their community members throughout this project.

The Challenge

As of April 2021, Queens had the second highest total number of COVID-19 related cases and fatalities out of the five boroughs of New York City². The overwhelming majority of these cases originated from neighborhoods that are largely home to underserved populations. Despite concerted efforts by city and state agencies to limit the transmission of the virus and to vaccinate large numbers of residents, these areas continue to retain some of the highest overall infection rates within the city.

The Approach

The Get Tested Queens Project is a coalition comprised of leaders from local faith-based organizations to provide free and easily accessible testing services, in addition to culturally tailored outreach and education. Key activities include:

- Provide training and education for community members about COVID-19 testing and vaccination topics during monthly 'Health and Resource Fair' at each partner organization.
- Provide funding to increase capacity for COVID-19 testing activities.
- Generate COVID-19 testing communication materials.
- Evaluate strategies for the communication of test results through the creation of a direct testing phone line service and email.
- Collaborate with CEAL program on activities.

Contact: Semi Sung, GTQ Project Coordinator, Korean Community Services of Metropolitan New York (KCS), semi@kcsny.org

Find out more: <https://www.kcsny.org/>

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The Get Tested Queens project...

Served Black/African American, Hispanic/Latino, Asian American, Native Hawaiian and other Pacific Islander, socioeconomically disadvantaged, and sexual and gender minority populations

Supported COVID-19 vulnerable populations including community dwelling older adults, individuals with disabilities, homeless populations, individuals with medical comorbidities known to increase risk of severe COVID-19, children, individuals living in congregate housing, and migrant and immigrant communities

Key Benefits

CLINICAL

Provided COVID-19 testing services at community testing events.

COMMUNITY

Improved the ability for underserved populations to gain entry to and receive testing and vaccination services.

COMMUNITY

Directly addressed testing and vaccine hesitancy through the development and distribution of educational materials.

COMMUNITY

Developed a phone line service to provide an avenue for communication of test results and follow up.

ECONOMIC

Provided funding to faith-based organizations to promote COVID-19 testing.

KCS
WWW.KCSNY.ORG

THE KOREAN COMMUNITY
SERVICES OF METROPOLITAN
NEW YORK, INC.

²“Workbook: NYS-COVID19-Tracker.” New York State Department of Health COVID-19 Tracker, <https://coronavirus.health.ny.gov/covid-19-testing-tracker>

Make the Road New York was founded in 1977 and has led the way in securing justice and dignity for working and immigrant New Yorkers. Their survival services put \$70 million annually back into the pockets of participants and allow families to begin to pull themselves out of poverty. Over the past 20 years, Make The Road New York has organized initiatives that have secured hundreds of millions of new dollars in public investments in affordable housing, provision of translation and interpretation services, public health programs, and protection of civil rights. The organization has made a dramatic impact on the lives of millions more through broad-based policy victories, including statewide worker protections and expanded rights for immigrants in New York City and Long Island.

C2G PROJECT SUMMARY

Make The Road New York serves migrant and immigrant communities living in Queens, New York. They serve on New York City's Test and Trace Community Advisory Board and advocate for accessible healthcare and reliable information in the languages of local immigrant communities. The project promoted COVID-19 testing and education through the creation of culturally-tailored materials distributed through in-person outreach by community lay health workers (*promotoras*), workshops, and social media. The objectives of the project were to:

- Create and disseminate accurate, bilingual, and culturally competent materials on the Covid-19 virus.
- Hold "Know Your Rights" trainings for community members online.
- Wage advocacy campaigns to promote policies that protected the working class New Yorkers during the pandemic.
- Staff a Coronavirus hotline for vulnerable communities

The Community You Serve

Make the Road New York, is New York's largest immigrant-led community-based organization. It is best situated to defend and organize immigrant communities in critical moments. As a result of deeply entrenched systems of oppression, working class and immigrant communities face overcrowded and under-resourced schools; economically drained resources, health, and jobs from immigrant neighborhoods; LGBTQIA+ immigrants are over-policed in school and on the streets; and many immigrant families live in constant fear of separation.

C2G PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The COVID-19 Testing Outreach & Education project resulted in:

- **1,300 individuals reached** through outreach activities.
- **17,720 flyers distributed.**
- **Two Facebook Live events** conducted in Spanish with a total of **4,200 views.**
- **Development** of a COVID-19 NYC Vaccine guide.

The Engagement

Make The Road New York offers a variety of [services](#) to migrant and immigrant communities throughout the five boroughs in New York from their Brooklyn, Queens, & Staten Island office locations that includes:

- [Adult Literacy](#)
- [Civic Engagement](#)
- [Community Organizing](#)
- [Health Access](#)
- [Leadership Development](#)
- [Legal Services](#)
- [Youth & School Programs](#)

and more!

To learn more about the services offered at Make The Road New York visit: <https://maketheroadny.org>

The COVID-19 Testing Outreach & Education Project

Make the Road New York's deep relationships in New York immigrant neighborhoods and bilingual, community-driven approach enables the effective provision of critical COVID testing education and support. Their decades-long experience in immigrant health access makes them a trusted resource for those seeking to impact "hard to reach" immigrant communities.

RADx-UP CDCC
Community
Collaboration Grant
Program

IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The COVID-19 Testing Outreach and Education project led by Make the Road New York resulted in community and public health benefits.

Bilingual, culturally-responsive training and education were provided for community members around COVID-19 testing topics. Materials were tailored to the target population which included Spanish-speaking immigrant and working-class communities in New York and distributed via multiple methods to maximize reach.

The Challenge

New York immigrant communities are among the hardest hit by the COVID-19 pandemic, with the early epicenter of the crisis located in central Queens, the most diverse urban area in the United States.

The Approach

Led by a team of Community Health Workers and *Promotores*, peer health advocates, community members are encouraged to get tested, respond to calls from contact tracers, and practice COVID safety measures, as well as assist individuals in accessing testing appointments. Key activities include:

- Conduct Facebook Live/Zoom events or workshops providing COVID-19 updates, testing and vaccine information
- Distribute materials via food pantries
- Provide in-person and remote outreach to communities through the distribution of materials on COVID-19 testing information.

Populations Served

Served Black/African American populations, Hispanic/Latino populations, and socioeconomically disadvantaged populations

The Team: Health Department Outreach Team at Make the Road NY

Contact: Becca Telzak, Make the Road New York, Principal Investigator and Deputy Director, rebecca.telzak@maketheroadny.org

Find out more: <https://maketheroadny.org/>

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The COVID-19 Testing Outreach & Education project resulted in:

1,300 individuals reached through outreach activities

17,720 flyers distributed

Two Facebook Live events conducted in Spanish with a total of **4,200** views

Development of a COVID-19 NYC Vaccine guide

Key Benefits

COMMUNITY

Promoted health care accessibility by tailoring outreach activities and educational resources to the target community.

COMMUNITY

Utilized innovative methods to distribute bilingual educational resources related to the improvement of health on a community basis.

COMMUNITY

Connected undocumented and uninsured immigrants to free COVID-19 testing sites throughout New York City.

Translational
Science
Benefits Model

The National Hispanic Christian Leadership Conference (NHCLC) – Connecticut

Community Collaboration Grant (C2G)

ORGANIZATION PROFILE

The National Hispanic Christian Leadership Conference (NHCLC) is America's largest Latino Christian organization. The Connecticut chapter serves the Hispanic Evangelical churches, multiple denominations, and Clergy Associations in the state—representing 300 churches. The NHCLC is a large community of leaders who gather the community for networking and fellowship as well as to create strategic partnerships for public policy advocacy. The NHCLC promotes life, family, stewardship, education youth, and justice.

C2G PROJECT SUMMARY

The National Hispanic Christian Leadership Conference (NHCLC) – CT aimed to positively impact their communities and reduce the reach of COVID-19 in Bridgeport and Stamford, CT through:

- Dissemination of reliable and fact-based education, and
- Community-based interventions such as COVID testing and vaccine distribution.

The NHCLC–CT planned increased participation in COVID-19 testing and vaccination among Hispanic congregation members in Connecticut through the following activities:

- Increased participation through community outreach clinics
- Clergy-specific training to ensure pastors and deacons are well-prepared to disseminate facts from the pulpit.
- Increase capacity within Hispanic churches to better serve their residents; respond to COVID-19 concerns and fears through education, training, and credible, culturally tailed print materials
- Town halls to connect community residents to Latino medical personnel

The Community Served:

The Connecticut Chapter of the National Hispanic Christian Leadership Conference (NHCLC) is part of the largest Latino National Hispanic Evangelical in America. We are part of a movement that led millions of Hispanic Born Again Christ followers via our 40,118 Evangelical congregations by providing leadership, networking, fellowship, strategic partnerships and public policy advocacy platforms to our seven directives: Life, Family, Great Commission, Stewardship, Education, Youth and Justice.

C2G PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The **Faith-based Education & Outreach in Bridgeport** project which resulted in:

- Approximately **10,000 COVID-19 tests** distributed
- **Over 500 people reached** through vaccination clinics
- **Approximately 250 community members and 35 community pastors and leaders reached** through educational sessions
- **Dissemination** of reliable and fact-based educational materials

The Engagement

The NHCLC offers variety of programs to their community which consist of:

- [Faith & Education Coalition](#)
- [IGNITE- Youth Program](#)
- [Compassionate Evangelism](#)
- [Biblical Justice](#)

and more!

To learn more about the services offered at the Connecticut chapter of NHCLC visit: <https://nhclc-ct.org/>

To learn more about the services offered at NHCLC visit: <https://www.nhclc.org/>

The Faith-based Education & Outreach in Bridgeport, CT Project

The Faith-based Education & Outreach in Bridgeport, CT positively influences 5,000+ Connecticut residents using virtual and in-person town hall meetings to educate and encourage COVID-19 testing and vaccination.

RADx-UP CDCC
Community
Collaboration Grant
Program

IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The Faith-based Education and Outreach in Bridgeport, CT project had clinical, community and public health, and economic benefits.

Through their COVID-19 Community Pastoral Response Center, the project provided resources to faith leaders and congregants to have the most up to date information about the virus and vaccination to increase participation in COVID-19 testing and vaccination among Hispanic congregation members in Connecticut.

The Challenge

The harsh impact of the pandemic on marginalized communities and communities of color has been well-documented. Hispanics and Latinos **are 1.7 times** more likely to contract COVID-19 than their non-Hispanic white counterparts and are **4.1 times** more likely to be hospitalized from COVID-19, and **2.8 times** more likely to die from COVID-19 (CDC, 2021).

The Approach

The National Hispanic Christian Leadership Conference– CT – is a network of 104 Hispanic congregations throughout Connecticut whose aim is to positively impact their communities and reduce the reach of COVID-19 in Bridgeport and Stamford, CT through:

- Development and dissemination of reliable and fact-based training and education in English and Spanish to be shared with congregations and the community
- Community- based COVID testing and vaccine distribution interventions
- Hosting town halls with medical doctors for clergy members and congregants
- Provide micro-grants to churches to support their participation

The Team: Southwest Community Health Center, Connecticut Dept. of Public Health, City of Bridgeport Public Schools, Association of Hispanic Evangelical Ministers of Greater Bridgeport, URU-The Right to B, Radio Amor 690 am, Iglesia Cristiana El Refugio, Iglesia de Dios Centro de Vida, Funeraria Luz de Paz

Contact: Abraham Hernandez, Executive Director of Nat'l Hispanic Christian Leadership Conference - CT Chapter, revhernandeznhclc@gmail.com

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The Faith-based Education & Outreach in Bridgeport project...

Served Black/African American, Hispanic/Latinx, and socioeconomically disadvantaged populations

Resulted in:

An estimated **150** people reached through training and education activities

An estimated **200** people reached through COVID-19 testing communication materials

Key Benefits

CLINICAL

COVID-19 testing and vaccination services performed to diagnose and/or prevent COVID-19.

COMMUNITY

Developed bilingual, health education resources that relate to the improvement of health on an individual and community basis.

COMMUNITY

Addressed equitable access to COVID-19 information and medical doctors through community-based clinics and town halls.

COMMUNITY

Collaborated with other community-based organizations to host vaccine clinics to increase COVID-19 testing and vaccine uptake.

ECONOMIC

Potential economic benefits by providing COVID-19 testing to individuals at no cost.

Translational
Science
Benefits Model

DREAM Community Advisory Board

India Home*, South Asian Council for Social Services, United Sikhs, Project New Yorker

Community Collaboration Mini-Grant

ORGANIZATION PROFILE

The DREAM CAB (Community Advisory Board) includes four community-based organizations that serve populations in Queens neighborhoods with a high concentration of South Asians. The DREAM CAB has a demonstrated track record of success in implementing strategies to facilitate community-clinical linkages, reducing food insecurity, and increasing social connectedness among South Asians in NYC. All strategies are rooted in community settings and use evidence-based practice of providing culturally-competent, in-language materials delivered by Community Health Workers (CHWs), peers and Community-Based Organization (CBO) staff.

The Community You Serve

DREAM coalition partner CBOs reach a wide range of South Asian community members and have particular expertise in offering culturally and linguistically tailored services to individuals from a diverse range of South Asian cultures, including, Bangladeshi, Gujarati, Punjabi, Indo-Caribbean, Afghani, Pakistani, Tibetan, Nepali, Tamil, Telugu, Malayalee, Marathi, Kannada, Sindhi, and Sinhala. Many South Asians served by these CBOs speak Hindi, Bangla, Punjabi, Urdu, Gujarati, Nepali, Tibetan, Tamil, or Guyanese Creole. Partners also engage community members in high-need areas who speak Mandarin, Cantonese, and Spanish. The groups served mostly practice Islam, Hinduism, Sikhism, Jainism, or Christianity. Partners reach South Asians across New York City in targeting neighborhoods in Queens, Brooklyn, and Manhattan. Most of the clients that DREAM coalition partner CBOs serve are immigrants, low income, experience Low English Proficiency, and low digital literacy. Older adults that these CBOs serve also often face comorbid conditions such as diabetes and hypertension and disabilities.

The Challenge

Main challenges include **COVID-19 fatigue** and **confusion on safety protocols** with the CDC vs. New York City. In addition, we have noticed that misinformation and myths regarding side effects of the COVID vaccine and **lack of access to in-language COVID-19 health information** are significant barriers in the community.

RADx-UP C2G PROJECT SUMMARY

The overall objective of Project SWAB-C was to increase COVID testing and reduce related disparities in NYC South Asian communities. Project SWAB-C maximized the reach and impact of trusted CBOs' efforts to increase testing through outreach primarily at houses of worship, including mosques, gurdwaras, temples, and churches, and small business settings, including pharmacies, grocery stores, and clothing stores. Partners conducted in-person community outreach in high priority zip codes where a risk for rise in cases or ongoing rise had been identified. Partners also disseminated PPE (masks & hand sanitizer) and information on public safety guidance, including COVID-19 testing and vaccination referrals. Partners built upon existing relationships with city agencies to offer mobile van testing and testing on site at community locations.

Key Organizational Accomplishments

CLINICAL

Implemented **28 testing events & distributed 20,700 testing kits** to community members

COMMUNITY

Leveraged existing community programming and outreach practices, **culturally congruent and trusted messengers**, to maximize the reach and impact of the project

COMMUNITY

Developed **culturally- and linguistically-tailored health materials** to make complex health information meaningful and relevant to communities

The DREAM CAB (Community Advisory Board) includes four community-based organizations that serves populations in Queens neighborhoods with a high concentration of South Asians. The DREAM CAB has a demonstrated track record of success in implementing strategies to facilitate community-clinical linkages, reducing food insecurity, and increasing social connectedness among South Asians in NYC. All strategies are rooted in community settings, and use evidence-based practice of providing culturally-competent, in-language materials delivered by CHWs, peers and CBO staff.

The Engagement

- India Home is dedicated to empowering and addressing the needs of the South Asian immigrant senior community in Queens, through culturally competent services. At India Home's centers, seniors find community and resources through a diverse range of programs and activities.
- South Asian Council for Social Services focuses on four major areas of healthcare: access and advocacy, senior services, food security and civic engagement. The staff speaks 19 different languages and serves all 5 boroughs of NYC and Long Island.
- United Sikhs is a NYC-based nonprofit organization that supports disadvantaged and minority communities through community education and economic, social, and spiritual empowerment. Services include: legal aid, humanitarian aid, civil and human rights, and support services, creation of educational materials, food assistance, healthcare access, and service referrals.
- Project New Yorker is a community-based nonprofit organization in Queens that works to address the needs of low- to moderate-income (LMI) Bangladeshi and South Asian immigrant women and youth, many of whom come from a conservative Muslim background. Their work directly impacts over 15,000 people, helping to improve their lives through a variety of social services, mental health services, educational and digital literacy support, along with advocacy and civic engagement.

C2G PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

Project SWAB-C resulted in:

- Hosting **28 testing events**
- Distributing **20,700 testing kits**

The Future

Our coalition aims to continue providing guidance to South Asian communities on COVID-19 safety measures as needed according to the conditions as they evolve over the next few years. We aim to continue addressing health equity while providing outreach to communities through addressing food security, financial security, housing security, and other factors, to help ensure our communities are educated and resourced to a more equitable level.

The team:

Shaaranya Pillai, Rehan Mehmood, Jagjit Kaur,
Afsana Monir

Contact:

Shaaranya Pillai
shaaranya@indiahome.org
India Home, Inc.
Tel: (917) 834-7895

Find out more:

<https://indiahome.org/>
<https://unitedsikhs.org/>
<https://www.projectnewyorker.org/>
<https://www.sacssny.org/>

The SWAB-C

Through our collective reach in diverse South Asian communities, we will extend an exerted, sustainable effect on providing culturally tailored health information and access to COVID testing through partnership with and dissemination through trusted community locations, including house of worship and businesses, including grocery stores, restaurants, and pharmacies.

RADx-UP CDCC Community Collabora tion Grant Program IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The project resulted in clinical, community and public health, and economic benefits.

Project SWAB-C maximized the reach and impact of trusted CBOs' efforts to increase testing through outreach primarily at houses of worship, including mosques, gurdwaras, temples, and churches, and small business settings, including pharmacies, grocery stores, and clothing stores. Partners conducted in-person community outreach in high priority zip codes where a risk for rise in cases or ongoing rise had been identified. Partners also disseminated PPE (masks & hand sanitizer) and information on public safety guidance, including COVID-19 testing and vaccination referrals. Partners built upon existing relationships with city agencies to offer mobile van testing and testing on site at community locations.

The Challenge

Main challenges include COVID-19 fatigue and confusion on safety protocols with the CDC vs. New York City. In addition, the team has noticed **that misinformation and myths** regarding side effects of the COVID vaccine **and lack of access to in-language COVID-19 health information** are significant barriers in the community.

The Approach

Partnering with community organizations, local businesses, and houses of worship SWAB-C was able to provide testing and education regarding testing. Key activities include:

- Educating community members through both inreach and outreach, including educational sessions, street canvassing, tabling at events and day of action events to spread messaging on COVID-19 testing.
- Distributing tests and providing demonstrations on how to do them.
- Met regularly with academic stakeholders to receive guidance and improve strategies.

The Team: South Asian Council for Social Services, Project New Yorker & United Sikhs are completing project in collaboration with India Home.

Contact: Shaaranya Pillai

Email: shaaranya@indiahome.org

Phone: 917-834-7895

Find out more: www.indiahome.org

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The SWAB-C ...

Served Black/African American, Hispanic/Latino, Asian American, socioeconomically disadvantaged, and sexual and gender minority populations

Resulted in:

20,700 testing kits distributed

28 testing events held

Key Benefits

CLINICAL

Performed methods to diagnose COVID-19 symptoms.

COMMUNITY

Provided culturally- and linguistically-tailored health educational resources relate to COVID-19 on a community basis.

COMMUNITY

Leveraged existing community programming and outreach practices, culturally congruent and trusted messengers, to maximize the reach and impact of the project.

ECONOMIC

Potential to reduce financial costs of services to providers or consumers.

Translational
Science
Benefits Model¹

¹ Institute of Clinical & Translational Sciences at Washington University in St. Louis. Translational Science Benefits Model website. <https://translationalsciencebenefits.wustl.edu>. Published February 1, 2019. Accessed May 31, 2022.

ORGANIZATION PROFILE

The Center for Global Health Innovation (CGHI) identifies, champions, and addresses the health problems faced by the world that need the most attention. These are challenges that no one person or organization can solve alone. By organizing, accelerating, and supporting talented people and successful companies to innovate around these problems, The Center works to improve health outcomes for every community and every individual around the globe. By focusing on equity, these life-saving innovations create economic impact, build new industries, create more jobs, and open new global marketplaces to further empower community success. Only through rigorous, strategic, and active collaboration designed to deliver sustainable and profitable innovation will humanity overcome the Global Health challenges we face.

C2G PROJECT SUMMARY

The Global Health Crisis Coordination Center (GHC3) proposed a program to introduce, expand, and build confidence in COVID-19 testing in underserved, medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable Atlanta communities marginalized by poverty and race-based inequities. The program built upon the GHC3's extensive COVID-19 pandemic response experience, national messaging program (COVIED), and existing community network to increase the capacity for COVID-19 testing expertise, education, communication, and information dissemination by:

- Establishing an ongoing community presence and hosting community events at trusted sites
- Assisting essential community organizations, such as schools, to reopen safely
- Building trust with community members

The Community Served

Located in Atlanta, Georgia, CGHI is at the center of public health collaboration, discovery, and invention. Establishing a vibrant life sciences workforce and talent pipeline for future generations, CGHI has more than 700 stakeholders, partners, and members representing various voices across their community. These include:

- 300 community members,
- 191 from corporate entities,
- 158 from non-profits,
- 34 from healthcare and universities, and
- 21 from government.

C2G PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The Building confidence in COVID-19 testing in underserved and marginalized Atlanta populations project resulted in:

- **2,000 people reached** as part of testing efforts
- **8 community events hosted**
- **226% increase** in uptake of COVID-19 testing in schools
- **The distribution of COVID-19 rapid test kits** to over 2000 people in the community

The Engagement

The Center for Global Health Innovation currently employs two initiatives that offer a variety of programs to their communities, [GHC3](#) and the [Georgia Chapter of Women in Global Health](#) (WGH Georgia). WGH Georgia [brings together women](#) across the southern US to advocate for gender equality, bolster [women's leadership in global health](#), and to [stimulate thought and develop skills](#). GHC3 offers the following programs:

- [Community Outreach](#)
- [Vaccine Equity](#)
- [Healthy Schools](#)
- [Worship Action Coalition](#)
- [Economic Framework](#)
- [HEROES](#)

and more! To learn more about the services, programs, and initiatives offered at The Center for Global Health Innovation:

<https://cghi.org/>

CGHI Community COVID-19 Confidence Project

The CGHI Community COVID-19 Confidence Project aims to remove barriers to COVID-19 testing and increase testing capacity to reduce community transmission, lower impact on health, and ensure children can remain engaged in education through in-person learning.

RADx-UP CDCC
Community
Collaboration Grant
Program
IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The Center for Global Health Innovation (CGHI) Community COVID-19 Confidence Project resulted in community and public health benefits.

The project has established an ongoing community presence in an underserved area of Atlanta. The project increased community knowledge of the dangers posed by COVID-19, COVID-19 mitigation methods, and the importance of testing through the hosting of community events with trusted community partners in medically and socioeconomically vulnerable communities adversely affected by COVID-19. Testing was provided to the community at a time of short supply during COVID surges.

The Challenge

COVID-19 has had, and continues to have, a **disproportionate impact on economically disadvantaged and underserved communities**. These populations experienced significant challenges before the pandemic. COVID-19 closures and social distancing amplified those problems and dismantled the support systems that these communities rely on. The organizations and schools that form the backbone of that support system face uncertainty as they move to safely reopen.

The Approach

The objective of the project is to build upon the Global Health Crisis Coordination Center's extensive COVID-19 pandemic response experience, national messaging program (COVIED) and existing community network to:

- Establish an ongoing community presence and host community events at trusted sites to address urgent needs in underserved communities and reduce COVID-19 transmission through testing.
- Assist essential community organizations to reopen safely by providing resources and establishing and demonstrating repeatable and actionable guidance that includes COVID-19 testing.

Populations Served

Served Black/African American populations, Hispanic/Latino populations, and socioeconomically disadvantaged populations

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The CGHI Community COVID-19 Confidence project resulted in...

2,000 people reached as part of testing efforts

8 community events hosted

226% increase in uptake of COVID-19 testing in schools

Key Benefits

COMMUNITY

Increased uptake in school testing by 226%.

COMMUNITY

Distribution of COVID-19 rapid test kits to over 2000 people in the community.

COMMUNITY

Promotion of COVID-19 education and testing among underserved community populations through the hosting of community events.

The Team: Purpose Built Schools, Metro Atlanta Chamber of Commerce, Goodr, Common Market, Open Hand, Atlanta Public School System

Contact: Katie Shapcott, Center for Global Health Innovation, kshapcott@globalhealthc3.org

Find out more: <https://cghi.org/>

Translational
Science
Benefits Model

Mano Amiga is a nonprofit organization providing high quality education & community development services to children & families from low-income communities. It emerged in response to the need to mobilize and advocate against the detention and deportation of undocumented individuals in the US. Currently, their objectives have broadened to include advocating for criminal justice policy reform within Hays County. Their advocacy initiatives encompass community education on contemporary concerns, the collection and dissemination of data, facilitating access to resources and services, and nurturing community members directly affected by these issues into leadership roles.

C2G PROJECT SUMMARY

Mano Amiga specifically targeted vulnerable groups, including immigrants, non-English speakers, individuals affected by incarceration, and low-income neighbors, aiming to overcome prevalent social and cultural barriers, along with general socioeconomic risks impacting access to basic health resources in the community. The objectives of the project were to:

- Integrate COVID-19 testing education into vaccine outreach to address barriers and information gaps.
- Prioritize linguistically and culturally responsive education through community canvassing.
- Connect residents with vaccination and testing opportunities, organizing community-led clinics and town halls.

The Community You Serve

Mano Amiga initially operated as an immigrant rights organization, focusing on public education about immigration matters, securing individuals from deportation proceedings, and pushing for local criminal justice policy reforms. They persist in their commitment to advocate for immigrant rights. Mano Amiga San Marcos is dedicated to the mission of educating, advocating, coordinating, and organizing in support of immigrants and low-income residents in the rural I-35 corridor, spanning Guadalupe, Caldwell, Hays, and Comal counties, between San Antonio and Austin. In collaboration with urban partners, their goal is to establish an 80-mile-long stronghold against racist and anti-immigrant policies in the heart of Texas.

C2G PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The “Fuera Con El Virus: Increasing COVID-19 testing in Central Texas” project resulted in:

- Increased training, education, and information dissemination on COVID-19 testing
- Removing barriers to communication and outreach related to COVID-19
- Dissemination of simple-to-read education on testing topics
- **Over 10,000 people reached** as part of testing efforts

The Engagement

The Mano Amiga impacts its community by advocating for immigrant rights, pushing policy reforms, and securing individuals from deportation in the rural I-35 corridor.

The Mano Amiga offers a variety of [services](#) to residents in Texas, including:

- [Donate](#)
- Education
- Art and culture
- Entrepreneurship
- Health
- Environment

and more! To learn more about the services offered at Mano Amiga visit:

<https://www.manoamigasm.org/contact>

The Fuera Con El Virus: Increasing COVID-19 testing in Central Texas

The project will impact multiple vulnerable populations along the I35-corridor in Texas. It aims to result in an increase in COVID-19 testing and awareness of other strategies to mitigate the COVID-19 pandemic.

RADx-UP
CDCC Community
Collaboration Grant
Program
IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The project resulted in community and public health benefits.

Fuera Con el Virus project increased COVID-19 training, education, and information dissemination for communities with communication barriers.

The Challenge

The most prevalent barriers in underserved communities include social barriers in the form of misinformation and cultural barriers and general socioeconomic risk factors such as access to basic health resources. Lack of trust and action has placed the burden of managing, exiting, and recovering from the pandemic on local community-based organizations like Mano Amiga.

The Approach

The project uses population-specific strategies to reach vulnerable groups such as immigrants, non-English speakers, those impacted by incarceration, and low-income neighbors. Key activities include:

- Sharing culturally and linguistically responsive educational material at community events such as summer camps university events, park events, farmer's markets, local drag shows, etc.
- Hosting virtual and in-person *platicas*, or community conversations, and amplifying virtual, free, and research-backed training/ webinar activities.
- Infusing "infosnacks," easy-to-read facts regarding COVID-19 testing topics within our newsletters, correspondence with partners, clients, and volunteers, and within our regularly scheduled programming.

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The Fuera Con El Virus: Increasing COVID-19 testing in Central Texas...

Served Black/African American, Hispanic/Latino, Asian American, socioeconomically disadvantaged, and sexual and gender minority populations

Resulted in:

10,000 people reached as part of testing efforts

5 events held

Key Benefits

COMMUNITY

Increased accessibility to COVID-19 testing materials for Spanish speakers and immigrants.

COMMUNITY

Provided COVID-19 education and outreach to promote health on an individual and community basis.

The Team:

Contact: Eric Martinez, Executive Director Mano Amiga,
eric@manoamigasm.org

Website: <https://www.manoamigasm.org/>

Translational
Science
Benefits Model¹

¹ Institute of Clinical & Translational Sciences at Washington University in St. Louis. Translational Science Benefits Model website. <https://translationalsciencebenefits.wustl.edu>. Published February 1, 2019. Accessed May 31, 2022.

The reNOUNce deNOUNce Gang Intervention Program operates as a non-profit organization, offering a ten-week intensive program tailored for at-risk juveniles and adults aged twelve and older. The program's overarching objective is to demonstrate the adverse impact of gang involvement on individuals, their families, and society at large. Focused on addressing issues such as bullying, peer pressure, conflict resolution, and decision-making, the reNOUNce deNOUNce Gang Intervention Program Corp. aims to guide participants toward making positive choices and disengaging from detrimental gang affiliations.

C2G PROJECT SUMMARY

The reNOUNce deNOUNce Gang Intervention Program aimed to mitigate the spread of COVID-19 among youth and underserved, vulnerable populations in Cleveland, Ohio. The objectives of the project were to:

- Utilize the organization's influence with youth and other underserved, COVID-19 vulnerable populations to distribute test kits and educational brochures across Cleveland.
- Target youth populations aged 11-25 for focused outreach and extend efforts to reach underserved and COVID-19 vulnerable populations of all ages through community outreach initiatives.
- Maximize distribution efforts to ensure broad coverage and accessibility of testing resources and educational materials within the community.

The Community You Serve

The reNOUNce deNOUNce Gang Intervention Program serves its community by offering a comprehensive 10-week program tailored for proven-risk youth aged 12-17, encompassing both males and females involved in gangs. Serving as both a deterrence and intervention, the hands-on program addresses critical issues such as bullying, peer pressure, conflict resolution, cognitive thinking, and decision-making. What distinguishes the program is the unique perspective brought by Laron's Douglas life experiences. The program's expansion into juvenile and adult rehabilitation facilities extends its expertise on gang-related matters, including seminars to train employees.

C2G PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The “Targeting Youth in Gangs & with Behavioral Issues” project resulted in:

- **Completion of** four large community pop-ups, six smaller pop-ups, and a YouTube channel, **reaching over 3,000 individuals**
- Increased education in lower socioeconomic areas
- **Distribution of over 1,000 tests**

The Engagement

The reNOUNce deNOUNce Gang Intervention Program positively impacts the community by providing essential resources and support to at-risk youth, helping deter gang involvement in Cleveland, Ohio.

The reNOUNce deNOUNce Gang Intervention Program offers a variety of [services](#) to residents in Ohio, including:

- Supporting Area School Districts
- Collaborating with education leaders Who Work with Proven Risk Youth
- Provide Tips from Consultants and Educators
- Giving Back to local communities
- Helping Juveniles and Adult Offenders

and more! To learn more about the services offered at reNOUNce deNOUNce Gang Intervention Program visit:

<https://www.renouncedenougangprogram.org/>

Hazte la Prueba: Testing for COVID within Indiana's Latinx Population

The project seeks to establish a bilingual registration call center run by the Learning Network and an after-hours vaccine/testing site run by Open Door Health Clinic (both with a history of service to Latinx residents) nurtured by the Clinton County Health Department, which has 19 months of experience in delivering high-quality support.

RADx-UP
CDCC Community
Collaboration Grant
Program
IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The project resulted in community and public health benefits.

Hazte la Prueba implemented a Spanish Help Line where community members can call and register (both in English and Spanish) for COVID-19 testing or obtain information regarding COVID-19 and where to get the vaccine

The Challenge

The needs of the Latinx community were particularly highlighted by the COVID-19 global pandemic, which caused inequitably high levels of job loss and economic instability. The vaccination rate of Clinton County remains under 50% and demands on the testing site have been heightened. The goals of this project are to increase education and awareness of COVID-19 testing and vaccination in Spanish by establishing a bilingual call center in the county and to make another site available for evening/weekend testing and vaccination to serve the needs of those whose working hours don't allow them to access testing/vaccination services during the current hours of operation.

The Approach

To promote community participation among Hispanic/Latino and underserved rural populations, key activities include:

- Hire and train staff to meet extended hours for the COVID-19 testing site.
- Establish a call center and provide bilingual staff (English and Spanish) to attend all the calls and texts received by community members requesting information or appointments for COVID-19 testing or vaccines.
- Bilingual staff attend community events to disseminate information and awareness about COVID-19 testing.

The Team: The Learning Network of Clinton County, Open Door Health Clinic, Clinton County Health Department

Contact: Melinda Grismer
Director of the Learning Network of Clinton County
melinda@lnocc.org

Find out more: www.lnocc.org

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

Hazte la Prueba: Testing for COVID within Indiana's Latinx Population...

Served Hispanic/Latino, underserved rural populations

Resulted in:

1,460 people reached as part of testing efforts

1,000+ people received instruction on how to administer home tests correctly

Key Benefits

COMMUNITY

Increased the ability for underserved populations to gain entry to and receive testing and vaccination services.

COMMUNITY

Trained bilingual staff to provide COVID-19 testing services to individuals in the community

COMMUNITY

Provided COVID-19 testing and vaccine education and outreach to promote health on an individual and community basis.

Translational
Science
Benefits Model¹

¹Institute of Clinical & Translational Sciences at Washington University in St. Louis. Translational Science Benefits Model website. <https://translationalsciencebenefits.wustl.edu>. Published February 1, 2019. Accessed May 31, 2022.

